

GS/ST/R16

7/1/80

Began excavation from surface of level 2. Level 2 was a thin layer of light brown sand over Level 3 and Level 4. Level 3 sand (clean yellow sand w/ few limestone, granite, calcite fragments, some piece of newspaper. We think that Level 3 is a fill level from previous excavations. This ^{hypothesis} appears to be confirmed by the existence of a limestone surface under Level 3. It appears that the sand level 3 is above a limestone block(?). Level 4 in the NE corner extending down the slope of the trench to @ 1.20 cm appears to be a level of hard packed brown sand w/ a large amt of medium to lg stone (limestone & quartz) and some yellow mud brick (or ferregerous limestone?). There were also several very sm fragments of charcoal in Level 2 above Level 4.

A ^{small} piece of aluminium foil wrapping ^{was} recovered from the back dirt from Level 3.